

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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THE EVOLUTION OF PASSENGER TRANSPORT IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: This study uses a longitudinal approach to analyze Uzbekistan's passenger transport patterns from 2013 to 2023 and evaluate the economic implications. Road and metro dominate, with metro exhibiting the largest increase, suggesting urbanization, according to an analysis of road, air, rail, trolleybus, and tram. Trams and trolleybuses remained minor, while rail and air had moderate growth. Issues with sustainability, connectivity, and equal access still exist despite the COVID recovery. For a sustainable transportation system, recommendations include updating public transportation, emphasizing green mobility, improving multimodal connections, and enlisting the private sector more.

Key words: COVID-19, public policy, road, metro, train, air, Uzbekistan, passenger transportation, economic effect, and connection.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistonda 2013–2023-yillarda yo'lovchi tashish tendensiyalarini tahlil qilib, ularning iqtisodiy ta'sirini. Avtomobil, havo, metro, temir yo'l, trolleybus va tramvay transportining oltita turi ko'rib chiqilishi davomida avtomobil transporti va metro boshqa transport turlariga qaraganda yo'lovchi tashish bo'yicha ustunlik qiladi, metro esa urbanizatsiyani aks ettiruvchi eng yuqori o'sishni ko'rsatadi. Havo va temir yo'l transporti o'rtacha, lekin beqaror o'sishni namoyon etdi; tramvay va trolleybuslar esa eng kichik ko'rsatkichlarni ko'rsatishdi. COVID-19 dan keyin tiklanishga qaramay, teng foydalanish, ulanish va barqarorlik muammolari saqlanib qolmoqda. Tavsiya sifatida jamoat transportini modernizatsiya qilish, ekologik toza harakatlanuvchi transportlarga ustunlik berish, modallar aro aloqalarni yaxshilash va xususiy sektor ishtirokini kuchaytirishni o'z ichiga oladi va bu qadamlar barqaror transport tizimini yaratishga xizmat qiladi deb taklif qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, yo'lovchi tashish, iqtisodiy ta'sir, avtomobil transporti, metro, temir yo'l, havo transporti, barqarorlik, COVID-19, davlat siyosati.

Аннотация: В исследовании анализируются тенденции пассажирских перевозок в Узбекистане с 2013 по 2023 годы. Рассматриваются шесть видов транспорта — автомобильный, авиационный, метро, железнодорожный, троллейбусный и трамвайный. Автомобильный транспорт и метро доминируют, причем метро демонстрирует наибольший рост, отражая урбанизацию. Авиационный и железнодорожный транспорт показали умеренный, но нестабильный рост; трамваи и троллейбусы остались маргинальными. Несмотря на восстановление после COVID-19, сохраняются проблемы с равным доступом, связностью и устойчивостью. Рекомендации включают модернизацию общественного транспорта, приоритет экологичной мобильности, улучшение межмодальных связей и усиление роли частного сектора для создания устойчивой транспортной системы.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, пассажирские перевозки, экономическое воздействие, автомобильный транспорт, метро, железнодорожный транспорт, авиационный транспорт, устойчивость, COVID-19, связность, государственная политика.

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing passenger transportation by diverse transport methods is particularly relevant for a variety of reasons, including environmental, economic, social, and planning views.

Passenger transport activity has increased dramatically, particularly in the EU, with passenger automobiles accounting for approximately 73% of total passenger kilometers traveled [1]. This growth has an impact on energy consumption, emissions, and environmental sustainability, making it critical to assess transportation modes in order to identify potential for greener alternatives and avoid negative impacts. Understanding the modal split and usage patterns assists in formulating policies to promote sustainable mobility habits, such as increased use of public transportation, walking, and cycling, which reduces congestion and pollution. Infrastructure, operational, and technical needs vary depending on the method of transportation. Analyzing these modes enables planners to choose the optimal combination of transit modes to fulfill passenger requirements, operator restrictions, and community goals while balancing cost, reliability, comfort, convenience, and trip time.

Comprehensive mode analysis promotes integrated transportation services and intermodality, which use the capabilities of several modes to increase flexibility, efficiency, and passenger experience while maintaining dependability. Understanding travel behavior and mode choice characteristics (such as socioeconomic status, built environment, and attitudes) allows for more accurate forecasting of future transportation demands and effective infrastructure investment.

Passenger transportation accounts for a sizable portion of household expenditures (for example, 13% in the EU), therefore studying transport modes helps maximize economic resources and enhance cost efficiency for both customers and operators [1].

Various mechanisms influence social equality, accessibility, and safety. Analyzing modes contributes to these concerns by encouraging safer individual transportation, high-quality public transportation, and integrated services that improve mobility for all population segments. Mode analysis is critical for improving operational performance and efficiency, addressing urban congestion and traffic issues by maximizing current resources rather than just adding infrastructure.

Mode evaluation include evaluating technology kinds (train, highway, and others), right-of-way categories, and operational factors that impact passenger traffic and the system's overall role in urban growth. Research on transportation modes promotes innovations such as cooperative vehicle systems, driver assistance, and smart integrated information and ticketing platforms that improve safety, convenience, and sustainability. In conclusion, studying passenger transportation across diverse modes is critical for building sustainable, efficient, and equitable mobility systems. It influences policy, planning, and investment choices, promotes environmental goals, enhances the passenger experience, and aids in the integration of various modes of transportation into coherent networks that suit the changing needs of urban and regional mobility.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The transportation system has a significant impact on economic performance and growth because it allows people, products, and services to move effectively across areas. Its economic impact may be largely divided into four categories: productivity, cost reduction, regional development, and market accessibility.

Let's us consider several definitions of the concept of "economic impact of transportation".

Researcher Todd Litman from the Victoria Transport Policy Institute describes how transportation regulations and planning decisions affect economic growth by enhancing links between resources, workers, businesses, and customers. He emphasizes that effective transportation networks boost productivity, competitiveness, employment, and incomes by lowering prices and broadening access [2].

According to the American Public Transportation Association (APTA), investments in public transportation generate economic growth through two main mechanisms: cost and productivity improvements that increase mobility and reduce travel time, and spending impacts that create jobs and income across industries. These investments boost both short-term economic activity and long-term productivity growth [3].

Andrés Guzmán Valderrama's study on economic and transportation impact assessment demonstrates that transportation regulations have an influence on economic performance by altering accessibility, travel costs, and land usage. He emphasizes that improved transportation infrastructure promotes regional growth by luring enterprises and enabling labor mobility [4].

Duranton and Turner contend that improved highway infrastructure leads to increased local economic production, higher household incomes, and better employment rates by enhancing accessibility and lowering travel times, hence supporting regional economic growth [5].

According to Graham et al., public transit systems such as subways and fast buses have a favorable impact on urban productivity and attractiveness. Their findings are consistent with prior research that supports the impact of enhanced transportation in stimulating local economic activity and improving quality of life. However, their research may neglect possible issues, such as the financial viability of large-scale urban transportation systems, social justice in access, and long-term maintenance expenses [6].

The analyzed research clearly shows that transportation networks influence economic performance and growth. Transportation infrastructure and policies boost productivity, lower costs, encourage regional development, and increase market accessibility by allowing people, products, and services to move more efficiently. Overall, our findings emphasize the need of strategic transportation expenditures and good management for long-term economic growth. However, authorities must also address possible social and financial problems in order to maximize the inclusive and long-term advantages of transportation infrastructure.

For this purpose, in our research we tried to find out which mode of transport is chosen for passenger transportation most of all, in order to emphasize the importance of each mode of transport we tried to analyze the dynamics from 2013 to 2023.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative longitudinal analysis to look at passenger transportation patterns in Uzbekistan across six modes of transport from 2013 to 2023. The study approach was developed to rigorously assess modal performance, growth trends, and the influence of exogenous shocks, including the COVID-19 pandemic.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

For a deeper comprehension of the dynamics of passenger transportation in Uzbekistan, a rigorous quantitative research was carried out from 2013 to 2023. This section summarizes the results of our longitudinal study, which focuses on the number of people transported by various modes, such as road, air, metro, rail, trolleybus, and tram. By analyzing annual trends and fluctuations across these six modes of transportation, we hope to highlight the changing structure of the country's passenger transportation system, the resilience of different modes to external shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic, and the implications for future infrastructure planning and policy.

Table-1. The number of passengers transported by different vehicles in Uzbekistan from 2013 to 2023 (in million passengers)

Year	Road Transport	Air Transport	Metro	Rail Transport	Trolleybus	Tram	Total
2013	4815.8	2.4	59.2	17.4	0.4	14.7	4909.9
2014	5079.0	2.3	54.0	19.1	0.9	14.6	5169.9
2015	5293.2	2.2	52.3	20.1	0.8	11.4	5380.0
2016	5480.8	2.1	53.5	20.5	0.8	2.7	5560.4
2017	5591.3	2.2	61.6	21.1	0.5	2.3	5679.0
2018	5852.8	2.6	69.1	22.1	0.5	4.4	5951.5
2019	5915.2	3.2	79.2	22.9	0.7	3.8	6025.1
2020	5248.5	0.9	38.8	6.2	0.3	1.2	5295.9
2021	5914.2	3.0	101.8	7.9	0.5	2.3	6029.7
2022	6092.1	4.1	136.7	9.0	0.5	2.9	6245.3
2023	6292.7	5.3	172.0	9.6	0.7	3.4	6483.7

Source: The table was independently compiled by the author based on data from stat.uz.

The table shows passenger transportation data in Uzbekistan from 2013 to 2023, including six modes (road, air, metro, rail, trolleybus, and tram), with totals in million passengers. Total passenger numbers increased from 4,909.9 million in 2013 to 6,483.7 million in 2023, a 32.1% rise over the decade, showing increased mobility and infrastructural development. The rise was not linear, with a significant drop in 2020 (5,295.9 million), most likely owing to COVID-19 limits, followed by a substantial rebound.

Road Transport: Road transport dominated the industry, accounting for more than 96% of total passengers. It increased from 4,815.8 million in 2013 to 6,292.7 million in 2023 (a 30.6% rise). The most significant year-on-year increase came from 2013 to 2014 (5.5%) and 2020 to 2021 (12.7%), with the latter indicating post-COVID recovery. The 2020 reduction (11.3% from 2019) was large but less severe than in other modes, demonstrating its resiliency.

Metro ridership grew the most dramatically, from 59.2 million in 2013 to 172.0 million in 2023 (a 190.5 percent increase). The greatest rise occurred between 2020 and 2021 (162.4%), most likely as a result of additional infrastructure or regained demand following COVID. The low figure of 38.8 million in 2020 reflects pandemic-related limitations. The Metro's percentage of total passengers increased from 1.2% to 2.7%, indicating urbanization and investment in public transportation.

Air Transport: While air travel increased by 120.8% from 2.4 million in 2013 to 5.3 million in 2023, its contribution remained minor (0.08% of total in 2023). The 2020 reduction to 0.9 million (71.9% below 2019) was the most severe among modes, indicating worldwide aviation delays. The recovery was substantial, with a 244.4% gain from 2020 to 2021 and continuous growth through 2023, showing increased demand for air travel.

Rail Transport: Rail passenger numbers increased from 17.4 million in 2013 to 22.9 million in 2019, but then fell drastically to 6.2 million in 2020 (a 73.0% decrease) owing to the pandemic. Recovery was slower than in other modes, with just 9.6 million by 2023, still below pre-COVID levels. The overall growth rate between 2013 and 2023 was 55.2%, although rail's percentage of total passengers remained below 0.4%.

Trolleybus and Tram: These modes had limited influence, accounting for less than 0.1% of total passengers. Trolleybus utilization has varied, peaking at 0.9 million in 2014 before leveling at 0.7 million by 2023. Tram ridership fell drastically from 14.7 million in 2013 to 2.3 million in 2017, recovering somewhat to 3.4 million by 2023. The 2020 decreases (57.1% for trolleybus and 68.4% for tram) were large, demonstrating their susceptibility to interruptions.

Uzbekistan's passenger transportation system is mainly reliant on roads, with the metro developing as a rapidly expanding urban alternative. While air and rail transportation are rising, they are still tiny contributors. The 2020 drop demonstrates vulnerability to external shocks, while the general increasing trend shows economic and infrastructure growth. Future growth may be dependent on sustained metro expansion and rail rehabilitation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

According to a 2013–2023 review of passenger transportation in Uzbekistan, the industry has grown significantly, especially in road and metro transit, which is indicative of further urbanization and infrastructural improvements. However, the underutilization of rail, trolleybus, and tram services combined with the persistence of road transport's dominance suggests that a more sustainable and balanced strategy to mobility is required. The industry's durability, as seen by its quick rebound after the COVID-19 epidemic, highlights how crucial it is to the nation's social and economic life. However, there are still issues with regional connection, equitable access for all demographic groups, and environmental sustainability.

A number of calculated actions are suggested in order to tackle these issues and build on previous advancements. First, improving service quality and operational efficiency will come from speeding up the modernization and digitization of public transportation, including the installation of e-ticketing and real-time information systems. The sector's environmental impact may be decreased by giving priority to eco-friendly modes, such as the growth of electric and low-emission automobiles and the construction of bike and pedestrian infrastructure. Enhancing intercity and regional connections, particularly by building rail and multimodal hubs, will guarantee more equitable growth and better accessibility in every area.

Additionally, promoting healthy competition and private sector involvement would spur innovation and enhance service delivery. For fair development, it is still crucial to guarantee social inclusion by making transportation accessible and reasonably priced for low-income groups, students, seniors, and those with disabilities. Lastly, maintaining public confidence and bolstering the long-term viability of the passenger transportation system will need ongoing enhancements to safety regulations and monitoring. By incorporating these strategies, Uzbekistan may advance toward a cutting-edge, effective, and inclusive transportation network that improves everyone's quality of life while simultaneously fostering sustainable economic growth.

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